

Whose Fairness? For Whom?

Value Gaps in AI Ethics and the Conditions for Institutionalization

Aoi Miyazaki

Chiba University Data Science Core

This study examines whose conception of fairness is prioritized in the social implementation of generative AI and how value gaps shape institutionalization. A web-based survey of 600 respondents, including AI practitioners and general users, reveals a systematic divergence in fairness perceptions. Practitioners emphasize procedural fairness and transactional legitimacy, while general users prioritize outcome equality and protection of vulnerable groups. Gender-based differences further indicate variation even within expert communities. These findings show that assumptions embedded in AI development do not fully align with societal expectations. The study argues that effective institutionalization requires recognizing multiple fairness conceptions, incorporating diverse stakeholder perspectives, and establishing governance mechanisms that allow continuous revision to maintain social legitimacy.

1. Fairness for Whom?: Problem Setting and Research Background

With the development of generative AI and the rapid proliferation of AI driven by its widespread adoption, and the rapid proliferation of AI enabled by the generalization/democratization of AI development its social impact and ethical concerns are becoming increasingly apparent. As AI increasingly replaces human decision-making, ethical conflicts surrounding human judgment and value judgments are a pressing issue and the background for this research. Those involved in artificial intelligence possess specialized habitus (embodied ways of thinking) formed through education and vocational training, which may influence their definition of "fairness." This research focuses on the differences in perceptions of fairness between AI practitioners and AI beneficiaries. While previous AI ethics research has often taken fairness for granted, it has not sufficiently examined how its definition differs depending on social attributes and positions. This study visualizes the divergence of the concept of fairness in AI ethics through a survey of public opinion, positions these differences as risks and foundational conditions for institutional design, and sets the problem as the implicit assumption that "fairness" in AI ethics is shared as a single normative concept. Furthermore, it empirically clarifies these differences and examines the institutional aspects of AI ethics.

This paper examines the need for a shared ethical foundation in design.

2. Survey Design and Empirical Analysis of Perceptions of Fairness

In this study, fairness was analyzed based on Rawls' theory, organizing it into three layers: (1) fairness of opportunity and procedure, (2) legitimacy in judgment and allocation, and (3) justice as a social consequence. As a result, artificial intelligence engineers showed a strong tendency to emphasize the legitimacy of procedures, such as algorithmic consistency and rule adherence, as well as the fairness of transactions, such as profit distribution in proportion to the costs invested. On the other hand, general respondents outside of artificial intelligence-related fields placed more emphasis on fairness in terms of consequences, such as equality of results including socially vulnerable groups and correction of disadvantages. A systematic difference in the definition of fairness was confirmed between the two groups.

Survey Overview, Analysis Methods, and Limitations of the Analysis

In this study, a web-based questionnaire survey was conducted in 2020 with n=600 participants. The participants were divided into two groups: members of the Japanese Society for Artificial Intelligence and members of the JDLA (Japan Deep Learning Association) as artificial intelligence professionals, and non-artificial intelligence engineers who were invited to cooperate through social media, etc., as the general group. It should be noted that the general group may include students and novice researchers, and therefore, when interpreting the response trends, it is necessary to assume that the degree of professional expertise is not uniform among the participants.

The questionnaire included respondent attributes (gender, age, and industry) and their self-perception of fairness and equality as ethical values, as well as their choices for each question. The responses were statistically processed to analyze how each group perceives fairness. This study aimed to explore the differences in perceptions of fairness between artificial intelligence engineers and beneficiaries and was not intended to provide a rigorous estimate that represents the entire population. Therefore, the statistical test results should be considered as auxiliary indicators for understanding trends, and the influence of sample composition and self-selection bias must be considered when interpreting the differences obtained. For this reason, this study focused on the consistency and directionality of the response distribution observed between attributes, rather than on the presence or absence of statistical significance itself.

2.1 Definitions of fairness and social perceptions by attribute

In response to the question regarding the definition of fairness (Figure 1), a tendency for a gradual dispersion was observed overall. This indicates that "fairness" is not a single criterion, but a concept that is interpreted in multiple ways. When examined by attribute, those involved in artificial intelligence were more likely to emphasize "the ability to compete under the same conditions and rules," and tended to view the consistency of procedures and rules as the core of fairness.

Figure 1: Questions regarding the definition of fairness

On the other hand, among general workers outside of artificial intelligence-related fields, there was a relatively higher proportion of responses emphasizing "equal distribution of profits, services, and rights" and "not favoring any particular person," indicating a strong tendency to use the validity and impartiality of results as criteria for fairness. These differences reflect the differences in value perceptions formed by habitus, suggesting that the understanding of fairness has different structures depending on attributes.

Furthermore, an analysis of perceptions of fairness by social attributes (Figure 2) revealed significant differences based on gender and occupation. Overall, women tended to perceive the current situation as unfair more than men across all attributes. In particular, among those involved in artificial intelligence, men were more likely to perceive the current situation as fair, while women in this group and those with other attributes showed a relatively stronger sense of unfairness.

This indicates that differences in perceptions of fairness exist based on gender, even within groups that share expertise. Furthermore, it suggests that differences in the definition of fairness may influence divergent perceptions when evaluating people with disabilities.

Figure 2: Perceptions of fairness by attribute

2.2 Differences in the structure and perception of expectations regarding AI

Differences were also observed among the attributes regarding perceptions of the impact of AI on social justice (Figure 3). Those involved in artificial intelligence tended to view the current society and institutions as generally fair, and showed a cautious stance towards significant corrections or changes brought about by AI. On the other hand, artificial intelligence...

General workers outside of those directly involved in the field have relatively strong expectations that the introduction of AI will improve social justice.

Figure 3: Perceptions of the impact of AI on social justice

These results indicate that expectations and evaluations surrounding AI differ depending on the attributes, and a crucial consideration in designing AI ethics is how to connect the careful awareness of engineers with the improvement expectations of users.

3. Interpretation of the Justice Gap and its Ideological Context

The analysis in Chapter 2 revealed that the understanding of "fairness" systematically differs depending on whether one is involved in artificial intelligence or not, as well as on gender and position. These results suggest the risks of relying solely on the sense of fairness of a specific professional group when embedding AI ethics into institutional frameworks. This study attempts to theoretically

position the need for institutional design that incorporates multiple perspectives, taking into account the differences in the sense of fairness across attributes. Those involved in artificial intelligence tend to place a strong emphasis on formal aspects such as procedural consistency and retribution for good and evil, and perceive the current system as relatively fair. In contrast, general users tend to place an emphasis on the validity of results and consideration for the protection of vulnerable groups, and expect improvements through AI.

This difference suggests that the habitus of engineers, formed through education and professional training, may have internalized value judgments that prioritize rationality and efficiency. In other words, the gap in perceptions of fairness is presented not as an individual difference, but as a structural phenomenon rooted in professional and social views.

3.1 Risks to AI Implementation Due to Discrepancies in Perceptions of Fairness

The divergence in perceptions of fairness poses multiple risks in AI implementation. Firstly, AI judgments are based on inherently opaque machine learning models, and their reasoning processes are not always fully explainable to both users and developers. Secondly, when AI is offered as a social service, users tend to over-trust its judgments and accept them uncritically due to "automation bias." Thirdly, the repeated use of AI judgments over the long term risks solidifying biases and discrimination inherent in the initial stages into social practices, which are then reproduced as if they were "common sense."

These risks are not limited to technical issues; they are amplified when AI is integrated into institutions without correcting differences in the understanding of fairness. On this point, Klaus (ICRC) points out that even when AI is used as a decision-making aid, it can stifle human responsibility and critical judgment by structuring the assumptions and options for judgment in advance, suggesting that the issue of fairness in AI implementation is an institutional and ethical challenge that goes beyond technical specifications.

3.2 Connecting with the intellectual currents surrounding AI ethics

In discussions surrounding AI ethics, Rawls' theory of justice is an important framework of reference, as fairness has functioned as a fundamental moral law of society. However, the understanding of so-called fairness varies depending on an individual's social background and professional training, and is inevitably influenced by the concept of habitus, as pointed out by Bourdieu. For this reason, Frankfurt's argument, which emphasizes sufficiency that does not threaten dignity, is suggestive from the perspective of ensuring minimum ethical standards while acknowledging the diversity of values. On the other hand, accelerationism and neoconservative thought, which have gained influence in recent years, tend to prioritize efficiency and growth and relativize existing moral laws, creating ideological tensions in institutional design. The institutionalization of AI ethics requires adjustments based on the visualization of these current ideological conflicts. This paper does not discuss the merits or demerits of the ideological trends themselves, but rather refers to them as background conditions that influence institutional design.

4. Conditions and Conclusions for the Institutionalization of AI Ethics

Based on the above discussion, the central question in the institutionalization of AI ethics is, "For whom will fairness be guaranteed, and in what form will it be institutionalized?" The contribution of this

research lies, firstly, in empirically demonstrating that the definition of "fairness," which tends to be taken for granted in AI ethics research, may be understood differently depending on social attributes and professional habitus. Secondly, by repositioning the differences in perceptions of fairness across attributes as a problem of institutional design, it presents a theoretical basis for introducing a multifaceted perspective in the AI design process.

Differences in the perception of fairness are not merely differences in individual values, but also AI settings. This was a structural issue that could be inherent in the planning and operational processes.

Therefore, technological improvements alone are insufficient; it is crucial to consider from whose perspective and at what level fairness should be incorporated into the system as something that can be shared. In this chapter, based on previous empirical results and ideological considerations, we will examine the conditions for implementing AI ethics as an institution, starting from the question, "Fairness for whom?"

4.1 Conditions for embedding fairness in the system

To embed fairness into the system as AI ethics, it is necessary to start from the premise that multiple concepts of fairness coexist, rather than assuming a single value standard. Furthermore, it is necessary to establish a system in which stakeholders with diverse perspectives are involved at each stage of AI design and operation, and where the decision-making process can be mutually visualized and verified. In particular, an audit system that can externally scrutinize the judgments of groups of engineers who tend to rely on professional rationality is indispensable. Moreover, rather than defining and fixing fairness once, ensuring institutional flexibility that allows for revision in response to changes in social conditions and actual usage is a condition that supports the sustainability and social

legitimacy of AI ethics. As an implementation measure, it is envisioned that fairness will be institutionally reinforced by implementing ethical reviews at the model evaluation stage and audits with the participation of external stakeholders.

4.2 Conclusion: Prospects for a system that shares fairness

This study empirically revealed that "fairness" in AI ethics is not a universally shared concept, but rather involves different understandings depending on one's position, attributes, and professional background. In particular, the divergence in perceptions of fairness observed between artificial intelligence engineers and general users carries the risk of entrenching injustice and undermining institutional legitimacy, as it can be unconsciously incorporated into the AI design and operation processes.

The findings and ideological considerations of this study suggest the limitations of embedding a specific view of justice as the correct answer within an institution. Rather, what is important is to explicitly position the question of "fairness for whom?" as a premise in institutional design and to build a system that incorporates the very existence of diverse values. In the future institutionalization of

AI ethics, it is necessary to have institutional flexibility that allows for continuous verification and modification at each stage of design, operation, and evaluation, while ensuring a minimum level of fairness that does not infringe on dignity, rather than basing decisions solely on technical rationality and efficiency. We believe that it is only through such a framework that it is possible to form a relationship between AI and society in which fairness can be shared.

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